

SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE PLATELETS FROM ORGANOCLAY TEMPLATES AND THEIR REINFORCEMENT IN THERMOSET POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

Recently, several methods have been explored for synthesis of graphene nanoparticles. In this study, we have synthesized graphene platelets using a Cloisite 20A organoclay as precursor and copper (II) acetate as a catalyst. Known percentages of cloisite clay and copper acetate were mixed and heated at 900°C in an autogenic pressure reactor. The product is washed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to remove the metal and metal oxide impurities. The final product was rinsed with water, followed by ethanol several times and used for analysis. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Raman spectroscopy were used to characterize the as-prepared product. XRD results show that the as prepared product is multilayered graphene. Raman spectroscopy of as prepared graphene shows a G-band at 2800 cm⁻¹ and D-band at 1600 cm⁻¹. These results also indicate that the synthesized graphene consists of multilayers with disordered structure and these results are consistent with the X-ray diffraction analysis. The TEM analysis shows that the graphene sheets are few nanometer thick and microns in lengths. These graphene platelets were further infused in SC-15 epoxy resin using a non contact mixing method and tested for their thermal and mechanical properties of the polymer composite. The flexural test results show that the strength and modulus of the polymer composite are 99.4 Mpa and 2.77Gpa. These results show an improvement of ~11% over that of the neat epoxy polymer composites prepared in similar condition and lodgings. TGA and DSC results show that an improvement in glass transition temperature and also decomposition temperature as compared to the neat epoxy polymer composite. The thermal conductivity results show an improvement of 115% compared to the neat epoxy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene is a one-atom thick layer of carbon atoms that are arranged in a honeycomb two dimensional (2D) lattice. It is the thinnest nanosize sheet currently reported in literature [1-2]. These are sp² bonded carbon atoms arranged in a two dimensional hexagonal lattice as a single layer or graphite based materials; buckyball or C₆₀, Carbon nanotubes and Graphite, which is a 3D stack of graphene layers which are held together by van der Waals interactions. Recently graphene has become the most attractive nanomaterial, not only because it is the thinnest and strongest measured material ever known, but also because of its excellent electrical, thermal and optical properties, with high specific surface area and ease of chemical functionalization [2]. This is a semi-metal or a zero-gap semiconductor, with excellent electrical properties; these properties open numerous possibilities for applications in electronics, such as, touch screen panels, solar cells, flexible thin film transistors, liquid crystal displays, graphene batteries/super conductors and for thermal management [3-4]. It has excellent in-plane mechanical, structural and thermal properties; hence it is used as filler in composite materials. One of the most promising applications of graphene is in polymer nanocomposites and polymer matrix composites which incorporate nanoscale filler materials and show substantial property

enhancement when used as fillers [5]. Although many nanofillers such as CNF, and CNT, have long been used as nanofillers in polymer composites. The CNTs have shown remarkable improvement in properties, the high cost of production of CNTs have reduced their incident of use. Recent work on incorporating graphene nanoplatelets in nanocomposites has been focused on the use of graphene-based fillers derived from GO and these can exhibit high electrical conductivities and modulus. The reported stiffness and electrical conductivity of GO- derived filler materials are higher than those reported for nanoclay [6]. The experimental work on graphene has spanned over forty years [7] and pristine graphene which is a sp^2 -hybridized carbon layer free of hetroatomic defects has been produced by several routes [8]. The method used for graphene synthesis depends on, the required quality of the product, structural consistency, ease of fabrication and the cost of growth; these methods include growth by chemical vapor deposition (CVD), micro-mechanical exfoliation of graphite and growth on crystalline silicon carbide. Although most of these methods yield defect-free quality graphene with exceptional physical, thermal and mechanical properties, they do not yield large enough quantities for use as fillers in composite materials. For example, the CVD method, though gives high quality graphitic, it is very expensive to run and the quantity of the product is relatively very small. All these methods can be used to produce large quantities of graphene, but the cost is high. The clay that has been used as the precursor has layered structure and these layers are separated by nanosize spaces in between, during the synthesis process graphene is formed from an organic precursor inherent in the clay and are arranged in these layers. Since these layers are on the nanometre scale, the graphene is grown controllably into nanosizes; the clay when washed off leaves nanometer scale graphene as the final product. The autogenic pressure reactor (APR) method, which we used, yields reasonably high quality graphene and on large scale, it is also less expensive in terms of cost of production. To the best of our knowledge the autogenic pressure reactor has not been used in the synthesis of graphene. Therefore, our research seeks to synthesize graphene using the autogenic pressure reactor (APR) method and to determine its property enhancing abilities when used as a filler in composite materials. The objective of this research is to synthesize graphene by autogenic pressure reactor (APR) and use these graphene material in thermoset polymers as fillers.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Cloisite 20A nanoclay was purchased from the Southern Clay products Incorporated and used as a precursor with copper (II) acetate as the catalyst. Cloisite 20A is a natural montmorillonite which is modified with a quaternary ammonium salt. The color of the materials is off white with loose bulk, packed bulk and density of 7.35lbs/ft³, 13.55lbs/ft³ and 1.77g/cc respectively. Epoxy SC-15 parts A and B were purchased from Applied Poleramics USA and used as received.

2.2. Synthesis of graphene

The Cloisite 20A organoclay was used as the main source of carbon in the synthesis of graphene with copper (II) acetate as the catalyst. The organoclay and catalyst were used in the ratio of 9:1. The mixture of the clay and the catalyst was fed into a Swagelock assembly and tighten as close as possible to ensure no leak of the pressure. This was then inserted into tube furnace. The sample is heated to 900°C for one (1) hour and cooled to room temperature. The product is washed with hydrochloric acid (HCL) to remove the metal and metal oxides. The sample is then washed with water and centrifuged at 9000 rpm at room for 20 minutes. The process is repeated three times and finally washed with ethanol to easy drying. The final product was dried overnight using a desiccator.

2.3. Preparation of Polymer composite

Epoxy SC-15, part A and part B were used for fabrication of graphene/polymer composites. Various percentages (0.1 to 1wt%) of graphene were infused with epoxy resin. The part A of epoxy resin was mixed with various percentages of graphene powder (0.1, 0.5 and 1wt%) using an ultrasound

irradiation in a pulse mode at a rate of 20 seconds on and 20 seconds off. The part A and part B epoxy resin were then mixed at a ratio of 10:3 respectively as suggested by the supplier. The final mixture was mechanically stirred for 3 minutes and removed the air bubbles using vacuum desiccator. The bubble free resin mixture was finally poured into a ASTM standard flexure molds and cured at room temperature for 24hours. The post curing was carried out at 100°C for 6hours.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction analysis

XRD spectrum of as-synthesized and HCL treated are shown in figure 1. The Figure 1(a) shows the prominent peaks at 2θ values of 26 degrees a characteristic of graphene and at 36, 45 and 65 which are assigned to the metal and metal oxides (copper and copper (II) oxide). These impurities were removed after washing with HCL to obtain the final product shown in Figure 1 (b). This figure clearly show the prominent peak at 2θ , value of 26 degrees, which is assigned to the graphene.

Figure 1. XRD spectrum of synthesized graphene a) as-synthesized, b) after HCl wash

3.2. Raman Spectroscopic analysis:

Figure (2) depicts the Raman spectra of as-synthesized graphene and HCL washed sample. Figure 2(a) and (b) both represents a G-band and a D-band. The presence of the D-band is an indication of a disorder in the structure of the graphene. The G-mode is approximately 2780cm^{-1} and the D and D' modes are respectively 1592cm^{-1} and 1353cm^{-1} . The D-band is broad signifying that the graphene consist of a multilayer and not a single layer, it also splits into two (D and D') which means that there were some impurities or surface charges on the graphene produced. These results are consistent with the literature [9-10].

Figure 2. Raman spectrum of a) as-synthesized graphene b) after HCl wash

3.3. Transmission electron microscopy

TEM micrograph of synthesized graphene showed that they consists of several sheets and are in the crystalline form with a uniform structure. TEM micrographs obtained for multi-layer graphene, the sheets observed in figure 3 show they are multi-layers and few nanometer thick. These results are consistent with the Raman spectroscopic analysis.

Figure 3. TEM of HCL treated graphene

3.4. Flexural analysis

The flexural stress-strain curves are shown in figure 4 and the results are summarized in Table 1. These results clearly shows that the flexural strength and modulus increased by addition of graphene platelets. The neat epoxy flexural strength is $\sim 89\text{MPa}$ and modulus is $\sim 2.59\text{GPa}$. Where as the addition of graphene sheets increase the maximum strength to 99MPa and modulus to 2.77GPa . These results are consistent with the commercial graphene sheets infusion. It is also observed that the addition of synthesized graphene sheets increase the strain to failure is $\sim 50\%$ which is a significant.

4. Flexural Curves for synthesized and commercial graphene

Table 1. Flexural Tests results of polymer composites infused with commercially acquired and APR synthesized Graphene

Material	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Percentage Increase (%)	Flexural Modulus, GPa	Percentage Increase (%)
Neat	89.15	-	2.52	-
0.1 Com	99.44	11.54	2.66	5.56
0.5 Com	77.57	-12.99	2.71	7.54
1.0 Com	61.43	-31.09	2.59	2.78
0.1 Syn	99.47	11.58	2.77	9.92
0.5 Syn	95.37	6.98	2.46	-2.38
1.0 Syn	94.35	5.83	2.39	-5.16

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this research we have successfully synthesized graphene platelets by simple autogenic pressure reaction. The as synthesized materials is characterized using Rama spectrometer and X-ray diffraction and compared with the commercial graphene platelets. The graphene synthesized in the research is relatively less expensive than the commercially procured. We have also compared their effectiveness through addition of these graphene platelets in epoxy polymer and they show a significant improvements in strength and toughness. The as synthesized graphene powder is as good as commercially procured graphene.

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